

Effect of Comparison between Qingchangligan Granules and Qingchangligan Decoction on D-GalN/LPS-Induced Liver Injury in Mice

Xiangying Zhang^{1,2}, Tingting Ma³, Feng Ren^{1,2,#}, Xiuhui Li^{1,#}

¹ Beijing Youan Hospital, Capital Medical University. 8 Xitoutiao, Youanmen Wai, Fengtai District, Beijing 100069, China

² Beijing Institute of Hepatology, Capital Medical University. 8 Xitoutiao, Youanmen Wai, Fengtai District, Beijing 100069, China

³ School of Traditional Chinese Medicine, Capital Medical University. 10 Xitoutiao, Youanmen Wai, Fengtai District, Beijing 100069, China

Ethnopharmacological relevance: The Qingchangligan formula has two dosage forms, granules and decoction. Both of them have the same prescription; however, whether their protective effects are different remain elusive.

Aim of the study: To compare and evaluate the protective effect of the granules and decoction of Qingchangligan formula on acute liver failure (ALF) mice induced by D-galactosamine (D-GalN) and lipopolysaccharide (LPS).

Materials and Methods: ALF was induced by intraperitoneal injection of D-GalN (700 mg/kg) plus LPS (10 µg/kg). The granules and decoction of Qingchangligan formula were administered to mice in the same dose and at the same time point, respectively, with three doses of 50 mg/kg (on day 1, day 2, and day 3) prior to D-GalN/LPS injection by intragastric administration. The mice in different groups were sacrificed at 6 h after D-GalN/LPS injection, and liver samples and blood were collected for analysis.

Results: The different processed methods for the Qingchangligan resulted in a little component difference between the granules and decoction: the content of some ingredients, including Catalpol, Caffeic acid, Naringin, Emodin and Chrysophanol in granules, are higher than in decoction. Both of the two Qingchangligan formulas administration ameliorated liver injury, as evidenced by the decreased the lethality in ALF mice, the reduced transaminase levels and well-preserved liver architecture. However, the granules seemed to be more effective than the decoction in the ALF model. Mice pretreatment with the Qingchangligan formula reduced the expression of inflammatory cytokines and promoted autophagy in ALF model. Moreover, the effect on inflammation and autophagy of granules is more obvious than the decoction.

Conclusions: Our findings demonstrated that the granules and decoction of Qingchangligan formula both exert a protective effect against the pathophysiology of ALF, especially the granules is more efficacious, which provide a rationale for using of the different formulations of Qingchangligan formula.

Keywords: Granules; Decoction; Acute liver failure; Qingchangligan formula.

Introduction

Acute liver failure is a life-threatening critical illness and the clinical presentation usually includes hepatic dysfunction, abnormal liver biochemical values, and coagulopathy; encephalopathy may develop, with multiorgan failure and death occurring in up to half the cases^[1], which demands urgent medical care. The goal of treatment is to save part of liver function, which usually needed liver transplantation. During the procedure, Qingchangligan formula, a traditional Chinese medicine played an important role in the protection of liver function against liver failure^[2]. The PTA (prothrombin activity prothrombin time activity) of the patients with combination of Qingchangligan formula and western treatment were higher than the patients only with western treatment, and the mortality was lower in the group with Qingchangligan formula treatment. Qingchangligan Formula is a traditional Chinese medicine formula comprising five herbs: Rheum pal-

matum, dried Rehmannia root, Magnolia officinalis, Taraxacum officinalis and Fructus aurantii, which is used to treat liver failure for more than ten years.

As we know, there are several dosage forms of traditional Chinese medicine used in clinic regularly, such as granules, decoction, pills and so on. The earliest and traditional method for herbal medicine is decocting, which is used for long period. In recent years, granules, another preparation of herbal is developed and was used more frequently in clinic^[3]. Now, we prepared the Qingchangligan decoction and granules for patients. So the problem is coming: can granules be used as a substitute to traditional decoctions? Thus, the purposes of this study were (1) to examine the ingredient difference between the two Qingchangligan formulations, (2) to examine the role of the two Qingchangligan formulations in protecting the liver from lethal injury in response to D-GalN/LPS, (3) to evaluate the effect of two Qingchangligan formulations on the inflammation and autophagy in acute liver failure caused by D-GalN/LPS.

Materials and methods

HPLC of Qingchangligan granules and decoction

Qingchangligan granules was purchased from Kangren Tang

Correspondence: Xiuhui Li. E-mail: lixihui@sohu.com; Feng Ren. E-mail: renfeng7512@hotmail.com. Address: Beijing Youan Hospital, Capital Medical University. 8 Xitoutiao, Youanmen Wai, Fengtai District, Beijing 100069, China.

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Pharmaceutical. However, the decoction with same hospital prescription agreement was prepared by Youan Hospital Pharmacy. Modern chromatographic methods such as high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC, kromasil c18, AKZO NOBEL, Sweden) using a few compounds as markers have been developed to qualitatively or quantitatively compare the quality of dispensing granules and medicine decoction^[4,5]. The chemical pattern was analysed by HPLC with different UV detections. The compounds were eluted at a flow rate of 1 mL/min, using a gradient program. The reference standards were purchased from National Institutes for Food and Drug Control.

Animals and treatment

Male wild-type (WT, C57BL/6) mice (8-12 weeks old) housed in the specific-pathogen-free class experimental animal room in Capital Medical University were purchased from Capital Medical University (Beijing, China). All animal studies were approved by the Ethics Committee of the Capital Medical University (approval ID: AEEI-2016-106). The mice, except for the controls, were injected with D-galactosamine (D-GalN, 700 mg/kg, Sigma, St Louis, MO, USA) and lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 10 µg/kg, Invivogen, San Diego, CA, USA) intraperitoneally to induce ALF, and liver and serum samples were collected for future analysis^[6].

The Qingchanglingan formula, which is prepared through a hospital prescription agreement, consists of Rheum palmatum, dried Rehmannia root, Magnolia officinalis, Taraxacum officinale and Fructus aurantii. The granules was purchased from Kangren Tang Pharmaceutical and the decoction was prepared in dispensary of traditional Chinese medicine of You-An Hospital^[6]. The dosage of Qinchanglingan for mice was 9.1 times of the clinical adult dosage according to the equivalent dose conversion of humans and animal⁸, which was 50 mg/kg, and administered to mice once a day for three days prior to D-GalN/LPS injection by intragastric administration^[7].

Liver function tests and liver damage assessment

Liver injury blood markers, including serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST), were detected by using a multiparametric analyzer (AU 5400, Olympus, Japan), according to the manufacturer's protocol. Paraffin-embedded liver sections (5-µm thick) were fixed in formalin and washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), then were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and then the samples were observed with light microscopy, according to the standard protocol.

Quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction

Total RNA was isolated from liver using TRIzol reagent following the manufacturer's instructions. For RT reaction, a total of 1 µg of RNA was reverse-transcribed into cDNA using the SuperScript™ III First-Strand Synthesis System (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA). Quantitative PCR was performed with a Chromo 4 Detector (MJ Research, Waltham, MA). PCR amplifications was carried out with 1× Super Mix (Platinum SYBR Green qPCR kit, Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) for 50 cycles at 50°C for 2 min, 95°C

for 5 min, followed by of 95°C for 15 s and 60°C for 30 s.

Measurement of plasma cytokines

Mouse plasma samples were analyzed to determine the TNF-α, IL-1β, IL-18, IL-6 and IL-10 levels by using a ProcartaPlex™. A Multiplex Immunoassay from eBioscience (Austria) was used following the manufacturer's protocol^[6].

TUNEL assay

Apoptosis in liver sections was detected by terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase-mediated dUTP nick-end labeling (TUNEL, red fluorescence) using an In Situ Cell Death Detection Kit (Roche, Indianapolis, IN, USA). A negative control lacking the terminal transferase was also analyzed. Positive controls were generated by treatment with DNase. Nuclei were stained with 49,6-diamino-2-phenylindole (DAPI, 1 µg/mL) for 10 min. Images were examined on a Nikon Eclipse E800 fluorescence microscope^[6].

Detection of hepatic caspase-3 activity

Liver homogenates were prepared in lysis buffer provided by Chemicon according to the manufacturer's instructions. Caspase-3 activity in the mouse liver tissues was determined by a colorimetric caspase-3 assay kit (Chemicon International Co., California, CA, USA).

Western blot analyses

Protein of liver tissue were collected in radio immunoprecipitation assay (RIPA) buffer, containing protease and phosphatase inhibitors. After protein quantification (Pierce™ BCA Protein Assay Kit, Thermo), the same amount of proteins were treated with SDS-loading buffer, subjected to SDS-12% polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE), and transferred to polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membranes (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). The membranes were incubated at 4°C with rabbit antibodies against cleaved caspase-3, Atg7, Beclin-1, LC3, and β-actin (1:1000; Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, MA, USA) overnight. After the membranes were washed with Tris-buffered saline with Tween-20 (TBST), as secondary antibody, horseradish peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit (1:2000) were added in 10 mL of blocking buffer for 1 h at room temperature. After the membranes were washed 3 times with TBST for 30 min, protein expression was visualized by means of Electrochemiluminescence (ECL, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Rockford, IL, USA) and digitalized with ChemiDoc XRS System.

Immunofluorescence staining

Liver cryosections were fixed by cold methanol and then permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X100 in PBS. The sections were first incubated with 10% goat serum for 20 min and then with LC3 rabbit monoclonal antibody overnight at 4°C. The sections were incubated with Alexa Fluor 568 goat anti-rabbit IgG (1:200, Invitrogen, Grand Island, NY, USA) for 45 min. After the slides were washed with PBS 3 times, the nuclei were stained with DAPI (1 µg/mL, Shizebio, Shanghai, China) for 10 min. The slides were observed under a Nikon Eclipse E800 fluorescence microscope (Nikon Crop., Tokyo, Japan)^[6].

Statistical analyses

Results are expressed as the mean ± SD. Statistical analyses were performed using an unpaired Student's t test (for two groups) and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Bonferroni test (for more than two groups). Results were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ ^[6].

Results

Components differences between granules and decoction of Qingchangeligan

Under the experimental conditions with the same crude drug amount, compared to the decoction chromatogram, the number of peaks in granules chromatogram was larger and the majority of the peak response valuable. In the terms of the ten components that have measured, as showed in the HPLC fingerprint, the main peaks of the five herbs in the two formulations were consistent. In the granules, Catalpol and Verbasco-side-components of the dried Rehmannia root, Caffeic acid-components of Taraxacum officnala, Naringin and Neohesperidin-components of Magnolia officinalis, Emodin, Emodin ether and Chrysophanol-components of Rheum palmatum, Magnolol-components of Fructus aurantii, were larger than that of decoction. However, Rhein in decoction was a little larger than that of granules (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Comparison of granule and decoction of Qingchangeligan Formula by HPLC.

R. Reference standards; S1. Decoction; S2. Granule;
1. Catalpol 2. Caffeic acid 3. Verbasco-side 4. Naringin 5. Neohesperidin 6. Rhein 7. Emodin 8. Magnolol 9. Emodin ether 10. Chrysophanol

Qingchangeligan granules has more protective effect on the liver injury than decoction

We evaluated whether there is difference between Qingchangeligan granules and decoction in rescue the injury induced by D-GalN/LPS. Pretreatment with the Qingchangeligan formula for 3 days before D-GalN/LPS treatment resulted in protection against ALF. In the survival analysis (Fig. 2A), the mice in the D-GalN/LPS control group began to die 6 h after D-GalN/LPS in-

Fig. 2. Both of the Qingchangeligan formulations attenuate the liver injury induced by D-GalN/LPS in mice. Qingchangeligan+D-GalN/LPS-treated mice were administered the Qingchangeligan formula in three doses of 50 mg/kg (on day 1, day 2, and day 3) prior to D-GalN/LPS injection by intragastric administration (n=10). Control mice were pretreated with PBS (n=10).

A. The survival rates of mice were measured in the Qingchangeligan granules+D-GalN/LPS-treated group, Qingchangeligan decoction+D-GalN/LPS-treated group and the PBS+D-GalN/LPS-treated group (10 mice per group).

B. Serum AST and ALT enzyme levels from different groups.

C. H&E-stained sections are shown for the livers of different group mice.

jection, and the survival rate of these mice was 20% (2 of 10 mice) at the 24-h time point. However, the survival rate after treatment with the Qingchangligan granules was 70% (7 of 10 mice). And the Qingchangligan decoction pretreatment group began to die 12h after D-GalN/LPS injection accompanied with 60% survival rate. The sera and livers of the four groups were collected 6 h after D-GalN/LPS injection. Regarding liver damage, the serum ALT and AST levels of the D-GalN/LPS administration group were much higher than those of the Qingchangligan granules and decoction treatment groups (Fig. 2B); moreover, the liver architecture was well preserved in the Qingchangligan decoction group, which was less preserved than the granules group (Fig. 2C). These results demonstrated that treatment with the Qingchangligan formula ameliorates D-GalN/LPS-induced liver injury in mice, and the granules dosage has better protective effect.

Qingchangligan granules is more effective on inhibiting liver inflammation than decoction

As ALF is an inflammation-mediated hepatocellular injury process, the impact on inflammation level implicates the two formulations' protective effect. To compare the impacts of the Qingchangligan granules and decoction on the induction of inflammatory cytokines by D-GalN/LPS-induced ALF, the livers of the four groups were harvested 6h after D-GalN/LPS injection. The gene levels of pre-inflammatory cytokines were normalized by hypoxanthine phosphoribosyl transferase (HPRT) levels in the control group. Both of the Qingchangligan granules and decoction attenuated the expression of proinflammatory cytokines (Fig. 3A), including tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and interleukin-18 (IL-18). Compared with those in the ALF group, the pre-inflammation gene levels of the two Qingchangligan formula groups decreased sharply and the gene levels of granules group were much lower. Furthermore, we found that the two Qingchangligan formulations increased the level of the interleukin-10 (IL-10). However, the IL-10 level increased more significantly in granules group. And the results were supported by the serum levels of the protein expression (Fig. 3B). Qingchangligan intervened could also dropped down the level of IL-6 in serum, which is a high sensitive pro-inflammatory factor. Overall, both of the Qingchangligan formula protected mice from liver injury by suppressing liver inflammation and the granules formulation maybe more effective than the decoction.

Hepatocyte apoptosis decreased more sharply in Qingchangligan granules pretreated ALF mice than in decoction group

Hepatocyte apoptosis occurred in the early stage during the acute liver damage. In our primary study, Qingchangligan granules could reduce the hepatocyte apoptosis level in acute liver failure mice. To explore the potential protective different impacts against apoptosis between the granules and decoction, we first used TUNEL assay to quantify apoptosis cells in liver failure mice; the positive cells were the most in D-GalN/LPS group (Fig. 4A), whereas the apoptosis level were decreased in both of the Qingchangligan pre-treatment groups and the granules group displayed significantly fewer apoptotic hepatocytes. Moreover, consistently with TUNEL data, the caspase-3 activity (Fig. 4B) and

the levels of cleaved caspase-3 (Fig. 4C) increased after D-GalN/LPS injection, but this increase was attenuated by Qingchangligan decoction, and the granules played a more effective decrease.

Qingchangligan granules promotes autophagy more significantly than decoction in ALF mice

Our previous work has shown that autophagy plays an important protective role in the procedure of ALF^[8] and Qingchangligan formula attenuated liver failure by upregulated autophagy. So we evaluated whether dosage form had relationship with the effect on the autophagy level in ALF model. We examined the gene expression levels of the Atg7, Beclin-1 and LC3, which are involved in the autophagy pathway. Compared with the model group, the group received Qingchangligan granules pretreatment had the highest expression of the autophagy-related genes, while the decoction group followed (Fig. 5A). Similar results were observed in the western blot analyses (Fig. 5B). Importantly, the conversion of lipidated LC3I into LC3II was slightly increased in Qingchangligan granules group. Moreover, we detected the immunofluorescence staining for LC3 (green) in the mouse livers. Among the four groups, the group that received the Qingchangligan granules pretreatment showed a higher level of LC3 compared with the decoction group, and the level of LC3 in both of them increased than the model group (Fig. 5C).

Discussion

ALF is a devastating clinical syndrome with high mortality, which usually follows one or more precipitating events^[9]. Qingchangligan formula that practiced in clinical treatment for patients used to be decoction, which comply with traditional method. In recent years, Qingchangligan granules appeared and begun to apply. The problem is coming: whether there is difference in the efficacy and safety between granules and decoction of the same traditional Chinese medicines formula. Previous study has showed that Qingchangligan granules could attenuated inflammation in ALF mice, but the efficacy of the decoction has not been detected. In this research, we investigated the decoctions and granules from some aspects: (1) the main ingredients in granules was same as in decoction, but some components have high contents in granules; (2) both granules and decoction could improve liver damage in ALF mice, the effect of granules slightly better than the decoction; (3) both of the granules and decoction could up-regulated autophagy level and suppressed the inflammation in acute liver failure mice, and the granules seemed to be more efficacious.

There are many formulations of traditional Chinese medicine, including decoction (we called it jian ji), granules (we called it ke li ji), pills (we called it wan or dan) and so on. Each formulation has its advantages and disadvantages^[10,11]. The earliest method for traditional Chinese medicine is decocting. In decoction, different herbs with different quality are boiled together to meet different clinic patients conditions, which is easy to be adjusted at any time as the patients has new syndromes. However, there are also some difficulties during its usage^[12]. For example, not every patient could grasp the "boiling protocol", especially different herbs

Fig. 3. Both of the Qingchangligan formulations protect against ALF by regulating the inflammatory reaction. The gene expression levels of proinflammatory TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-18 and IL-10 6 h after D-GalN/LPS injection (n=10/group).

A. Gene expression levels of inflammatory-related cytokines, including TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-18, IL-10, in the livers of the mice in the control group, the D-GalN/LPS-induced ALF group, the Qingchangligan granules pretreatment group and Qingchangligan decoction pretreatment with D-GalN/LPS-induced ALF group were measured by qRT-PCR (n=10/group).

B. Protein expression levels in serum of inflammatory-related cytokines, including TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-18, IL-10 and IL-6.

should be treated at different time point or with some other herbs, which increased the instability of different batches of decoction. In this case, the irregular boiling method bring the difficulties in ensuring quality of the herbal ingredients and in the transportation and storage practice^[13].

Since decoction has these disadvantages, granules are used more and more widely in clinical practice^[14,15]. At same time, some questions coming: Could granules have advantages in the quality control, herbal preparation and storage than occur with decoctions? Could we use the granules completely instead of de-

coctions in future? The most important question is that: Is the granules' effectiveness and safety equal to the decoctions and how do we compare them? The clinicians and herbal medicine consumers are also concerned about these issues^[16,17].

People used to think that there may be a variety of chemical reactions take place in the traditional Chinese medicine, which caused different herb qualities in different formulations. From our data, there was not new ingredient produced after the five compositions decoct, and the main components in granules are consistent with decoction. Furthermore, some herbs had higher con-

Fig. 4. The Qingchangeligan formula inhibits hepatocyte apoptosis in D-GalN/LPS-induced ALF in mice (n=10/group).

A. TUNEL staining (red) of liver tissue 6 h after D-GalN/LPS administration. The representative images indicate that Qingchangeligan granules markedly decreased the number of TUNEL-positive cells than decoction in D-GalN/LPS-treated mice. Original magnification, $\times 200$. The quantification of apoptotic cells via TUNEL staining (mean \pm SD) is shown.

B. The hepatic protein expression of cleaved caspase-3 and β -actin was measured by western blots.

C. Caspase-3 activity assay 6 h after D-GalN/LPS injection.

tent in granule compared in decoction. Then, the next problem coming: whether the difference in content caused different effectiveness. Our previous study has showed that Qingchangeligan granules could protect liver injury in acute liver failure caused by D-GalN/LPS through promote autophagy to attenuate inflammatory response^[6]. In this study, we compared the protection in acute liver failure mice of the Qingchangeligan granules and decoction.

To further evaluate whether there is difference in the protective effect of the decoction and granules, we examined the relevant liver function indicators. Transaminase is an effective evaluation index of liver function^[18,19]. Increased transaminase levels indicate liver damage and decreased hepatic function, but both of the Qingchangeligan decoction and granules could reduce hepatic transaminase levels in acute liver failure mice and improve liver function status. However, the serum ALT and AST level was a little higher in decoction pretreatment group, which means that Qingchangeligan granules may be a little more effective in decreasing the liver function enzymes level.

The pathogenesis of acute liver failure is very complex, and a variety of factors can influence each other. The specific mechanism is not yet clear, and the inflammatory response plays a key role^[20]. In the D-GalN/LPS model, inflammation may be important mechanisms involved in hepatotoxicity^[21-23]. The results of liver tissue pathology showed that liver damage in mice with acute hepatic failure was severe, inflammatory cell infiltration was obvious, and the scope of congestion and necrosis was large. The effect of Qingchangeligan intervention on liver injury can be observed from the most morphological observation, and the granules to protect the liver slightly better than the decoction.

The macrophages in a liver with ALF can be triggered by a variety of and then release many inflammatory factors, which cause sustained inflammation, liver cell injury and necrosis^[24,25]. Pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-18, activate inflammatory effector expression, thus resulting in an acute response. Furthermore, IL-10, the anti-inflammatory cytokine, had a higher level in Qingchangeligan decoction pretreatment

Fig. 5. The comparison of different Qingchangligan formulations on promotion of autophagy in D-GalN/LPS-induced mice with ALF.

A. Gene expression levels of autophagy-related proteins, including LC3, Atg7, Atg5 and Beclin-1, in the livers of the mice in the control group, the D-GalN/LPS-induced ALF group, the Qingchangligan granules pretreatment group and Qingchangligan decoction pretreatment with D-GalN/LPS-induced ALF group were measured by qRT-PCR (n=10/group).

B. Protein expression levels of autophagy-related proteins, including LC3, Atg7 and Beclin-1, were measured by western blotting with β-actin as a control.

C. Representative immunofluorescence staining for LC3 (green) in the mouse livers. One experiment is shown. Original magnification, ×200.

group than that in the model group, combined with the highest level in Qingchangligan granules pretreatment group, which may

suggest that the Qingchangligan granules may have more protective effect in reduction of the inflammatory activity in ALF model.

Apoptosis is an important element in the early stage of acute liver failure. Primary research has demonstrated apoptosis is related to the initiation and progression of the inflammation response^[26]. Our previous study suggested that Qingchangligan formula alleviated the hepatocyte apoptosis, which was supported by the results of the TUNEL assay, the caspase-3 activation and protein expression^[6]. Therefore, we further investigated the effect of the Qingchangligan granule and decoction to determine whether the granule and decoction could also result the apoptosis decrease, to analyze the relationship between the protect effect and the dosage form. The TUNEL results indicated that Qingchangligan granule could significantly decrease the apoptosis and resulted in a hepatocyte protective effect, which was consistent with the results of caspase-3 activity and cleaved caspase-3 protein content.

Autophagy involves the sequestration of regions of the cytosol within double membrane-bound compartments, followed by lysosome-based degradation of the contents^[27]. As autophagy affects the effector cells of innate and adaptive immunity, which mediate the inflammatory response, autophagy activity influences the inflammation regulation in liver cell^[28-30]. Increasing evidence shows that autophagy exerts a protective effect in hepatocytes. We performed experiments to determine whether the formulation dosages of Qingchangligan formula affects autophagy regulation. Autophagic flux can be monitored by combining the measurements of LC3II. An increase in LC3II conversion indicates the induction of autophagic flux^[31]. Our preliminary results showed that the Qingchangligan granules up-regulates the autophagy-related genes Atg7 and Beclin-1 and increases LC3II conversion. This research demonstrated that the decoction could also promote autophagy during the progression of D-GalN/LPS-induced ALF, but the granules is more effective in upregulating the autophagy level in ALF through the suppression of liver inflammation.

The question of the relationship between the main components of traditional Chinese medicine and different dosage forms and its relationship with curative effect is a problem that is currently very much concerned. Our results showed that there is no significant difference in the overall curative effect of the two dosage forms, and the granules is slightly better in the liver protection and inflammation reduction, which may be related to some decrease of the ingredients contents during the decoction process. However, there are some limitations in our study, we will take further research on the correlation between the protective effect and the quantity of the different formulations contain and to observe the different effect of different dosage forms on liver failure patient.

Abbreviations

ALF, acute liver failure; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; Atg, autophagy-related gene; D-GalN, D-galactosamine; DAPI, 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole; H&E, hematoxylin and eosin; IL-1 β , interleukin-1 β ; IL-18, interleukin-18; LPS, lipopolysaccharide; PBS, phosphate-buffered saline; PAGE, polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis; PVDF, polyvinylidene difluoride; qRT-PCR, quantitative reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction; TBST, Tris-buffered saline

with Tween-20; TNF- α , tumor necrosis factor- α ; TUNEL, transferase-mediated dUTP nick-end labeling.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

XYZ, FR and XHL, as the principal investigators, were responsible for the concept and design of the study. XYZ performed the experiments of the study and wrote the manuscript. TTM conducted some of the experiments.

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